

GAGAATAAAC TAGTATTCTT CTGGTCCCCA CAGACTCAGA GAGAACCCGC 50
 CACC**ATGTTT** GTGTTCTGG TGCTGCTGCC TCTGGTGTCC AGCCAGTGTG 100
 TGAACCTGAC CACCAGAACA CAGCTGCCTC CAGCCTACAC CAACAGCTTT
 ACCAGAGGCG TGTACTACCC CGACAAGGTG TTCAGATCCA GCGTGCTGCA 200
 CTCTACCCAG GACCTGTTCC TGCCTTTCTT CAGCAACGTG ACCTGGTTCC
 ACGCCATCCA CGTGTCCGGC ACCAATGGCA CCAAGAGATT CGACAACCCC 300
 GTGCTGCCCT TCAACGACGG GGTGTACTTT GCCAGCACCG AGAAGTCCAA
 CATCATCAGA GGCTGGATCT TCGGCACCAC ACTGGACAGC AAGACCCAGA 400
 GCCTGCTGAT CGTGAACAAC GCCACCAACG TGGTCATCAA AGTGTGCGAG
 TTCCAGTTCT GCAACGA**CCC CT**TCCTGGGC GTCTACTACC ACAAGAACA 500
 CAAGAGCTGG ATGG**AAAG**CG AGTTCCGGGT GTACAGCAGC GCCA**CAACT**
 GCACCTTCGA GTACGTGTCC CAGCCTTTCC TGATGGACCT GGAAGG**CAAG** 600
CAGG**GCAACT** **TCAAGAAC** T GCGCGAGTTC GTG**TTTAA**GA ACATCGACGG
 CTACTT**CAAG** ATCTACAGCA AGCACACCCC TATCAACCTC GTGCGGGATC 700
 TGCCTCAGGG **CTTCTCTG**CT CTGGAACCCC TGGTGGATCT GCCCATCGGC
 AT**CAACAT**CA CCCGG**TTTCA** GACACTGCTG GCCCTGCACA GAAGCTACCT 800
 GACACCTGGC GATAGCAGCA GCGGATGGAC AGCTGGTGCC GCCGCTTACT
 ATGTGGGCTA CCTGCAGCCT AGAACCTTCC TGCTGAAGTA **CAACGAGA**AC 900
 GGCACCATCA CCGACGCCGT GGATTGTGCT CTGGATCCTC TGAGCGAGAC
AAAGTGCACC CTGAAGTCCT TCACCGT**GGAAAAGGGC**ATC TACCAGACCA 1000
 GCAACTTCCG GGTGCAGCCC ACCGAATCCA TCGTGCGGTT CCCC**AAATAT**C
 ACCAATCTGT GCCCCTTCGG CGAGGTGTTT AATGC**CAC**CA GATTGCCTC 1100
 TGTGT**ACGCC**TGGAACCGGA AGCGGATCAG C**AATT**GCGTG GCCGACTACT
 CCGTGCTGTA CAACTCCGCC AGCTTCAGCA CTTCAAGTG CTA**CGGC**GTG 1200
 TCCCCTA**CCA**AGCTGAACGA CCTGTGCTTC A**CAAAC**GTGT ACGCCGACAG
CTTCGTGATC CGGGGAGATG AAGTGCGG**CA** GATTGCCCT**TGGACAGACAG** 1300
 GCAAGATCGC CGACTACAAC TACAAGCTGC CCGACGA**CTTCA**CCGG**CTGT**
 GTGATTGCCT **GGAA**CAGCAA CAACCTGGAC **TCAAAGT**CG GCGGCAACTA 1400
 CAATTACCTG TACCGGCTGT**TCC**GGAAGTC CAATCT**GAAG** **CCCTT**CGAGC
 GGGACATCT**CCACC**GAGATC TATCAGGCCG GCAGCACCCC **TTG**TAACGGC 1500
 GT**GGAAG**GCT TCAACTGCTA CTTCCCACTG CA**GTCCTACG**GC**TTTCAGCC**
 CAC**AAATG**GC GTGGGCTATC AGCCCTACAG AGTGGTGG**TGCT**GAGCTTCG 1600
 AACTGCT**TGCA**TGCCCTGCC ACAGTGTGCG GCCCTAAGAAAGCAC**CAAT**
 CTCGTGA**AGA**AC**AAAT**GCGT GAACTTCAAC TTCAACGGCC TGACC**GGC**AC 1700
 CGGCGTGCTG ACAGAGAGCA ACAAG**AAGTT** **CCTGCC**ATTC CAGCAGTTTG
 GCCGGGATAT CGCCGATACC ACAGACGCCG TT**AGAGATCC** CCAGAC**ACTG** 1800
GAAATCCTGG A**CATCACCC****TTG**CAGCTTC GCGGGA**GTGT** **CTGTGATCAC**
 CCCTGGC**ACC AAC**ACC**AGCA**AT**CAGGTGGC** **AGTGCTGTAC** **CAGGACGTGA** 1900
 ACTGTACCGA AGTGCCCGTG GCCATTCACG CCGATCAGCT GACACCTACA
 TGGCGGGTGT ACTCCACCGG CAG**CAATG**TG TTT**CAGACCA** **GAGCCGGCTG** 2000
TCTGATCGGA GCCGAGCA**CG** TGAACAATAG CTAC**GAGTGC** **GACATCCCCA**
 TCGGCGCT**GG**AATCTGCGCC AGCTACCAGA CACAGACAAA **CAGCCCTCGG** 2100
 AGAG**CCAGAA** GCGTGGCCAG CCAGAGC**ATCA**ATTG**CCTACA** CAATGTCTCT
 GGGCGCCGAG **AACA****GCGTGG** CTTACTCCAA CAACTCTATC GCTATCCCCA 2200
CAACTTCAC **CATCAGC****GTGAC****CAC**AGAGA TCCTGCCTGT GTCCATGACC
 AAGACCAGCG TGGACT**GCAC** CAT**GTACATC** TGCGGCGATT CCACCGAGTG 2300
 CTCCAACCTG C**TGCTGCAGTAC**GGCAGCTT C**TGCACCCA**G CTG**AATAGAG**
 CCCTG**ACAGG** GATCGCC**GTG** GAACAGGACAAGA**ACCCA** **AGAGGTGTTT** 2400
 GCC**CAAGTGA** AGCAGATCTA **CAAGAC**CCCT CCTAT**CAAG**G ACTTCGGC**GG**
 CT**CAATT**C AGCCAGATTC TGCCCGATCC TAGCAAGCC**CAG**CAAGCGGA 2500
GCTTCATCGA GGACCTGCTG TTCAACAAAG **TGACA**CTGGC CGACGC**CGGC**
 TTCATCAAGC AGTATGGCGA TTGTCTGGGC GACATT**GCCG** CCAGGGA**TCT** 2600

GATTTGCGCC CAGAAGTTTAACGGACTGAC AGTGCTGCCT CCTCTGCTGA
 CC**GATGAGAT GAT**CGCCCAG **TACACATCT**G CCCTGCTGGC CGGCAC**AAT**C 2700
 ACAAGCGGCT GGACATTTGG AGCAGGCGCC GCTCTGCAGA TCCCCTTTGC
 TATGCAGATG GCCTACCGGT TCAACGGCAT CGGAGTGACC CAGAATGTGC 2800
 TGTACGAGAA CCAGAAGC**TG AT**CGCCAACC AGTTCAACAG CGCCATCGGC
 AAGATCCAGG ACAGCCTGAG CAGCACAGCA AGCGCCCTGG GAAAGCTGCA 2900
 GGACGTGGT**C AACCA**GAATG CCCAGGCACT GAACACCCTG G**TCAAGCAGC**
 TGTCTCCAA **CTTC**GGCGCC ATCAGCTCT**TG TG**CTGAACGA TATCCTGAGC 3000
 AGACTGGACC **CTCCT**GAGGC CGA**GGTGCA**G ATCGACAGAC TGATCACAGG
 CAGACTGCAG AGCCTCCAGA CATACTGAC CCAGCAGC**TG ATCAGAGC**CG 3100
 CCGAGATT**AG AGCCTCTGCC AATCTG GCCG CCACCAAGAT GTCTGAGTGT**
GTGCTGGGCC AGAG**CAA GAG AGT**GGACTTT TGCGGCAAGG GCTACCACCT 3200
 GATGAGCTTC **CCTCAGTCTG CCCCTCA**CGG CGT**GGTG**TTT C**TGCACGTGA**
 CATA**TGTGCC** CGCTCAAGAG **AAGAATTTCA CCACC**GCTCC **AGCCAT**CTGC 3300
 CACGACGGCA **AAGCC****CACTT TCCT**AGA **GAA GG**CGTGTTTCG TGTCCAAC**GG**
CACCCAT**TGG TT**CGTGACAC AGCGGAACTT CTACGAGCCC CAGATCATCA 3400
CCACCGACAA CACCTTCGTG TCTGGCAACT GCGACGTCGT GATCGG**CATT**
 GTGAA**CAATA** CCG**TGTA**CGA CCCT**CTGCAG** CCGAGCT**GG ACAGCTTCAA** 3500
 AGAGG**AACTG** GACAAGTA**CT TTAAGAACCA** CA**CAAG**CCCC GACGTGGACC
 TGGGCG**ATAT** CAGCG**GAATC**AATGCCAGCG TCGTGA**ACAT** CCAGAAAGAG 3600
 ATCGACCGGC TGAACGAGGT G**GCCAAGAAT** C**TGAA**CGAGA GC**CTGATCGA**
CCTGCAAGAA CTGGGGAAGT AC**GAGCAGTA** CATCAAG**TGG CCCTGGGTACA** 3700
 TCTGGCTGGG CTTTATCGCC **GGACTGATTG** CCATC**GT GAT GGT CACAAT**C
 A**TGCTGT**GTT GC**ATGACCAG** **CTGCTGT**AGC TGCCTGA**AAGG GCTGTTGTAG** 3800
CTGTGGCAG**C TGCTGCAAGT** TCGACGAGGA CGAT**TCTGAG CC****GTGCTGA**
AGGGCGTG**AA**ACTGCAC**TAC ACATGATGAC** TCGAGCTGGT ACTGCATGCA 3900
 CGCAATGCTA GCTGCCCTT TCCCGTCCTG GGTACCCCGA GTCTCCCCCG
 ACCTCGGGTC CCAGGTATGC TCCACCTCC ACCTGCCCA CTCACCACCT 4000
 CTGCTAGTTC CAGACACCTC CCAAGCACGC AGCAATGCAG CTCAAACGC
 TTAGCCTAGC **CACACCCCA** CGGGAAACAG CAGTGATTAA CCTTTAGCAA 4100
 TAAACGAAAG TTTAACTAAG CTATACTAAC CCCAGGGTTG GTCAATTTG 4150
 TGCCAGCCAC ACCCTGGAGC TAGCAAAAAA AAAAAAAAAA AAAAAAAAAA
 AAAAGCATAT GACTAAAAA AAAAAAAAAA AAAAAAAAAA AAAAAAAAAA
 AAAAAAAAAA AAAAAAAAAA AAAAAAAAAA AAAAA